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Research Article

**KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDE AND PRACTICE OF DENTISTS
PRESCRIBING ANTIBIOTICS IN PERIODONTAL DISEASES**Dr Zara Rizwan¹, Dr Musab Azhar², Dr Kaynat Siddique¹¹de'Montmorency College of Dentistry, Lahore, ²Dental Surgeon, Tehsil Headquarter Hospital Sarai Alamgir Gujrat.**Article Received:** October 2020**Accepted:** November 2020**Published:** December 2020**Abstract:**

Introduction: Antibiotic resistance (AR) has become one of the most serious global issues of concern for health development today, threatening our ability to treat common infectious diseases.

Objectives: The main objective of the study is to analyse the knowledge, attitude and practice of dentists prescribing antibiotics in periodontal diseases.

Material and methods: This cross sectional study was conducted in de'Montmorency College of Dentistry, Lahore during September 2019 to March 2020. A self-completed questionnaire containing both closed and open ended questions was developed.

Results: Ninety-four (67.1%) of the respondents had attended OPD of the hospital on antibiotic use in the last one year, 8.6% at least once in the last two years, and 7.1% in the last five years while 4.3% reported not having had any since commencement of dental practice. House officers and the female respondents were significantly more influenced by the patients into prescribing antibiotics than their respective counterparts.

Conclusion: It is concluded that scientific basis for prescribing antibiotics for aggressive periodontitis was not respected by the majority of the participants.

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INTRODUCTION:

Antibiotic resistance (AR) has become one of the most serious global issues of concern for health development today, threatening our ability to treat common infectious diseases. AR can not only prolong illness, impose additional medical expenditure, and increase mortality, but also deter some common medical procedures, for example, caesarean sections, due to increased risk of infections [1]. There is a consensus that the misuse and overuse of antibiotics has contributed to the problem of AR. Inappropriate and over-prescription of antibiotics are prevalent worldwide. It was estimated that, in the USA, 30% of antibiotics are over-prescribed in outpatient settings, and the percentage of inappropriate antibiotic prescriptions can be as high as 50%. Irrational use of antibiotics is an even more serious problem in developing countries because of their fragile regulation systems and a lack of human capacity [2].

Physicians play a critical role in the global campaign against AR, simply because prescriptions are required for antibiotic usage. It is essential to understand how physicians prescribe antibiotics. Several systematic reviews concluded that both intrinsic factors (such as knowledge and attitudes of physicians) and external factors (such as system and organizational environment) have shaped the antibiotic prescribing behaviors of physicians. However, our understanding about their underlying mechanisms is still limited [3]. Despite the existence of practice guidelines, physicians may defy the guidelines and prescribe antibiotics in order to meet patient expectations or to avoid potential confrontations and complaints from patients. This process could involve some further compromises given that most prescribers are likely to be aware of the side-effects of the overuse of antibiotics [4]. Adding to the complexity is the impact of contextual factors. Physicians can be incentivized by professional, financial, regulatory, and cultural factors. There is a particular shortage of research documenting how physicians prescribe antibiotics in developing countries [5].

Objectives

The main objective of the study is to analyse the knowledge, attitude and practice of dentists prescribing antibiotics in periodontal diseases.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This cross sectional study was conducted in de'Montmorency College of Dentistry, Lahore during September 2019 to March 2020. A self-completed questionnaire containing both closed and open ended questions was developed. The questionnaire included (i): general information, (ii): perception and knowledge of antibiotic resistance, (iii): reported management of oral problems, (iv): perceptions about oral infections and (v): perceptions of how people perceive oral problems. The socio-demographic characteristics of the young doctors were summarized using frequencies and percentages; cross tabulations were used to compare the respondents' score about practice regarding oral diseases with practice types; logistic models were performed to study the association between respondents' characteristics and score on reported practice. It also investigated their knowledge of prescribing antibiotics in systemic conditions such as diabetes, kidney disease, organ transplant, prosthetics, thrombocytopenia, asthmatic and cardiac diseases. Subjects' understanding of antibiotic therapy was tested in terms of effectiveness of types of antibiotics in periodontal cases either bacteriostatic, bactericidal or a combination of the two and the duration of antibiotic treatment in various examples of periodontal cases.

The data was collected and analysed using SPSS 19. Differences were considered statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

RESULTS:

Ninety-four (67.1%) of the respondents had attended OPD of the hospital on antibiotic use in the last one year, 8.6% at least once in the last two years, and 7.1% in the last five years while 4.3% reported not having had any since commencement of dental practice. House officers and the female respondents were significantly more influenced by the patients into prescribing antibiotics than their respective counterparts ($P = 0.001$, Table 1).

Table 01: Analysis of questionnaire according to frequency distribution

Variable	Response	Category	Prevalence (%)	P
Knowledge on prophylactic use of antibiotics	Correct	Dentist	69.2	0.001
		PHDO	31.3	
		Public	33.3	0.005
		Private	57.1	
Patients' influence on antibiotic prescription	Strong to very strong	Male	27.6	0.001
		Female	66.7	
		Young doctors	31.3	0.001
		PHDO	72.2	
Indications for culture and sensitivity	Correct	Public	44.4	0.02
		Private	69.2	
Use of systemic antibiotics in any disease	Yes	≤2 years of last antibiotic course	66.0	0.01
		>2 years of last antibiotic course	50.0	
Antibiotic use in any therapy	Always and frequently	≤5 years of graduation	49.0	0.001
		>5 years of graduation	33.3	

Table 02: Attitudes and behavioural intentions toward antibiotic prescriptions.

Measurement	Scores (Mean ± SD)			
	General Practitioner	Surgeon	Gynecologist	p-value
Attitude				
Fear	1.07 ± 0.64	1.00 ± 0.62	1.31 ± 0.54	0.002
Ignorance	1.32 ± 0.44	1.21 ± 0.41	1.26 ± 0.38	0.140
Behavioral intention				
Prescribe antibiotics for upper respiratory tract infections	3.94 ± 2.09	4.58 ± 2.57	3.92 ± 2.14	0.221
Prescribe antibiotics	0.84 ± 0.61	0.86 ± 0.73	0.95 ± 0.59	0.761
Reduce antibiotic prescriptions	1.31 ± 0.52	1.30 ± 0.54	1.36 ± 0.50	0.694

DISCUSSION:

Irresponsible prescription of antimicrobials (AMs) is the driving factor for the growing antimicrobial resistance (AMR) crisis. Appropriate utilization of drugs necessitates optimal prescription habits. Prescriptive mishaps include inappropriate usage of drugs in the form of polypharmacy, inadequate dosage, failure to adhere to medical guidelines and inappropriate selection of drugs [6]. Among the most commonly inappropriately prescribed drugs are antimicrobials with the problem of bacterial resistance to commonly used antibiotics becoming a world-wide burden.

Consequences of such resistance are grave, affecting both the economical and health sectors. These may take several forms including increased morbidity and

mortality, reduction in quality of antibiotic therapy, increased treatment costs, and un-justified loss of resources. These effects are more prominent in developing countries like Pakistan suffering both economical challenges and weak institutional foundations [7].

Adherence to appropriate prescriptive habits necessitates following the rational steps for optimal prescription including defining the correct diagnosis, planning a safe and effective treatment plan, appropriate drug selection, choosing the effective dosage and duration, writing the prescription, conveying enough information to the patients and evaluation of the treatment procedures according to the patient's responses [8].

In an effort to hinder antimicrobial resistance several parameters should be targeted including the inappropriate prescriptive practices. In order to achieve an improvement in this regard, an effective change in physician's behaviour should be sought [9]. Our results are different from those reported by Abazi and Mihani 2018. The study aimed to evaluate the aspects related to the pattern of prescription of antibiotics among dentists in Tirana region for periodontitis. It showed that dentists in the Tirana region tend to prescribe amoxicillin alone (32.5%) and its combination with metronidazole (12.1%) or with clavulanic acid is prescribed in the management of patients with aggressive periodontitis, in both localized and generalized forms [10].

CONCLUSION:

It is concluded that scientific basis for prescribing antibiotics for aggressive periodontitis was not respected by the majority of the participants. There is a need to develop guidelines and start continuing development programs to improve knowledge amongst young doctors, and to prevent antibiotic resistance.

REFERENCES:

- Giblin TB, Sinkowitz-Cochran RL, Harris PL, Jacobs S, Liberatore K, Palfreyman MA, et al. Clinicians' perceptions of the problem of antimicrobial resistance in health care facilities. *Arch Intern Med* 2004; 164: 1662-8.
- Fathi I, Sameh O, Abu-Ollo M, Naguib A, Alaa-Eldin R, Ghoneim D, et al. Knowledge, Attitudes, and Beliefs Regarding Antimicrobial Therapy and Resistance Among Physicians in Alexandria University Teaching Hospitals and the Associated Prescription Habits. *Microb Drug Resist* 2016; 23:71-8
- Pulcini C, Williams F, Molinari N, Davey P, Nathwani D. Junior doctors' knowledge and perceptions of antibiotic resistance and prescribing: a survey in France and Scotland. *Clin Microbiol Infect* 2011; 17: 80-7
- Srinivasan A, Song X, Richards A, Sinkowitz-Cochran R, Cardo D, Rand C. A survey of knowledge, attitudes, and beliefs of house staff physicians from various specialties concerning antimicrobial use and resistance. *Arch Intern Med* 2004; 164: 1451-6.
- Costelloe C., Metcalfe C., Lovering A., Mant D., Hay A.D. Effect of antibiotic prescribing in primary care on antimicrobial resistance in individual patients: Systematic review and meta-analysis. *BMJ*. 2010;340:1120. doi: 10.1136/bmj.c2096.
- Goossens H., Ferech M., Vander Stichele R., Elseviers M. Outpatient antibiotic use in Europe and association with resistance: A cross-national database study. *Lancet*. 2005;365:579–587. doi: 10.1016/S0140-6736(05)70799-6
- Lopez-Vazquez P., Vazquez-Lago J.M., Figueiras A. Misprescription of antibiotics in primary care: A critical systematic review of its determinants. *J. Eval. Clin. Pract.* 2012;18:473–484. doi: 10.1111/j.1365-2753.2010.01610.x
- McCullough A.R., Rathbone J., Parekh S., Hoffmann T.C., Del Mar C.B. Not in my backyard: A systematic review of clinicians' knowledge and beliefs about antibiotic resistance. *J. Antimicrob. Chemother.* 2015;70:2465–2473. doi: 10.1093/jac/dkv164
- Akkerman A.E., Kuyvenhoven M.M., van der Wouden J.C., Verheij T.J. Analysis of under- and overprescribing of antibiotics in acute otitis media in general practice. *J. Antimicrob. Chemother.* 2005;56:569–574. doi: 10.1093/jac/dki257.
- Haubek D, Ennibi OK, Poulsen K, Vaeth M, Poulsen S, Kilian M. Risk of aggressive periodontitis in adolescent carriers of the JP2 clone of *Aggregatibacter (Actinobacillus) actinomycet emcomitans* in morocco: A prospective longitudinal cohort study. *Lancet* 2008;371:237-42.